

FIP Check: A Rubric-Based Tool for Assessing FAIR Implementation Profiles and Enabling Resources

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Abstract

As communities increasingly aim to understand and demonstrate how their data repositories support the FAIR Principles, decision-makers need tools that provide a clear, actionable snapshot. This paper introduces FIP Check, a framework for assessing FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) through a structured assessment of FAIR Enabling Resources (FERs). Built on the FIP ontology, the FIP Check brings three key innovations to FAIR assessment. First, it enables granular and practical evaluation by using a principle-aligned rubric to assess individual FERs. Second, it measures partial FAIRness through a progressive scoring scale that captures varying levels of FAIR alignment, offering constructive, context-aware feedback rather than purely binary results. Additionally, this tool complements existing FAIR assessment tools by focusing on FERs as the units of assessment rather than on entire repositories or datasets. Third, it ensures transparent and inspectable balance by embedding expert-informed assessments within a standardized rubric and making all scoring decisions directly visible. FIP Check was piloted across seven biomedical data repositories, testing its utility in identifying strengths and actionable gaps, and supporting more informed FAIR improvement efforts. It enables communities to assess their current practices and plan targeted enhancements. By providing detailed insights into how individual FERs contribute to FIP's FAIR alignment, the FIP Check transforms the FAIR Principles from abstract ideals into practical guidance—supporting strategic alignment, fostering shared understanding, and encouraging repository owners to see their resources not only as providers of data, but as infrastructure components.

Keywords

Open science, FAIR Principles, FAIR Assessment

1. Introduction

In today’s data-intensive research environments, stakeholders increasingly need structured and transparent ways to assess how repositories are engineered, governed, and interoperable (Wilkinson et al., 2016). The assessments are essential not only for understanding and improving data sharing within a community, but also for enabling meaningful comparisons across systems, increasing the value of data, and enhancing collaboration across communities (Wilkinson et al., 2016).

The FAIR Guiding Principles—15 Principles categorized for the contribution to Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability—provide widely referenced guidance for enabling machine-actionable and interoperable data (GO FAIR Foundation, n.d.-c). While they are intentionally high-level and avoid proscribing implementation details, this flexibility can lead to inconsistency in implementations and significant challenges in assessment (Hoebelheinrich et al., 2025; Jacobsen et al., 2020). Over the past years, a variety of tools have been developed to address these challenges, including automated evaluators such as F-UJI (Devaraju & Huber, 2020), the FAIR Maturity Indicators (FAIRmetrics & FAIRsharing, n.d.), FAIRChecker (Gaignard et al., 2023), and FAIR Enough (Maastricht University, n.d.). Each of these plays a valuable role—often focusing on assessing digital objects directly, frequently through automated tests tied to a specific interpretation of FAIR.

FIP Check (Kang, S., 2025; GO FAIR US, 2025) addresses a different but complementary need. Rather than evaluating datasets or repositories in their entirety, FIP Check is grounded in the FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP) ontology (Magagna et al., n.d.; see Figure 1), which enables communities to declare the technical solutions, called FAIR Enabling Resources (FERs), that they use to implement the FAIR Principles (Schultes et al., 2020). FIP Check offers a structured, rubric-based method for assessing how FAIR the declared FERs are and, in turn, how these FERs shape the FAIRness of the associated FIP. This shift in focus supports a more granular understanding of FAIRness and highlights targeted opportunities for improvement.

Figure 1. Core classes of the FIP ontology (from Magagna, et al., 2024). The FIP Ontology is a conceptual model that defines five main classes and their relations. At its core, the FIP Declaration connects FAIR Implementation Communities (FICs), FAIR Enabling Resources (FERs), and FAIR Principles, forming the foundation for FIP Check.

This distinction is important because evaluating FERs within a FIP allows communities to: (1) identify strengths and gaps at the level of specific FERs, and (2) compare and converge on shared solutions across domains, advancing interoperability.

In the following sections, we describe the rationale and structure of the FIP Check, present its innovations and scoring framework, and demonstrate its application through selected case studies. By grounding the assessment in declared, community-authored FIPs, FIP Check offers a structured and transparent way to interpret how FERs contribute to FAIRness.

2. Background

FIPs are a structured way for communities of practice to document how they implement the FAIR Principles for digital objects. While its primary purpose has been to support FAIR implementation planning and roadmapping for data and metadata, FIPs can be more broadly applied to any digital objects, including the FERs themselves. FIPs contain answers to specific implementation questions that are relevant to the FER(s) being documented. FIPs are constructed collaboratively through the FIP Wizard (GO FAIR Foundation, n.d.-a; Magagna et al., 2024).

FERs are the building blocks of a FIP, capturing the technical solutions—standards, services, specifications, or policies—used to enable FAIR implementations. There are 13 FER types, each linked to a specific FAIR principle and named according to its function (Magagna et al., 2024). Definitions and the corresponding FAIR principles are provided in *Appendix 1*.

An interesting concept of this model is that the FIP itself is also included as one of the 13 FER types, specifically under the R1.3 Principle. This reflects the understanding that the act of creating and maintaining a FIP is itself a community practice that demonstrates a commitment to FAIRness. In the FAIR2Adapt project (European Commission, 2024), ongoing efforts to provide input for automated assessment tools use the FIP to check whether the FERs it declares are actually applied to the evaluated digital objects, thereby adding a validation layer to the assessment process. The FIP Check approach to provide this validation is described in the Interpretive Decisions and Methodological Considerations section.

By making the FERs explicit, FIPs enable communities to communicate their FAIR implementation approach by understanding which FERs are in place and how they relate to specific FAIR principles. However, there is no systematic way to assess how well each of these resources contributes to FAIRness, nor to view the FIP in a consolidated and intuitive visualization. This lack of a framework makes it difficult for communities to recognize the effectiveness of their FERs and to pinpoint the areas for improvement.

3. Conceptual Innovations of FIP Check

FIP Check addresses this limitation by introducing a principled, rubric-based approach that shifts the assessment focus from entire repositories or datasets to individual FERs declared in a FIP. In doing so, it brings the underlying structure of FIPs to life, enabling communities to make informed decisions about where to focus their FAIR improvement efforts.

3.1. Granular and practical evaluation of FERs within FIPs

Unlike other FAIR assessment tools such as F-UJI or FAIR Maturity Indicators, which evaluate datasets or repositories against a specific interpretation of FAIR, FIP Check focuses on the individual FERs

declared in a FIP. Each FER is scored using a set of Principle-aligned questions to assess the degree to which each FER advances specific FAIR principles. These FER-level assessments are then aggregated across the 15 Principles, the four Principle Categories, and the entire FIP.

This layered approach makes it possible to pinpoint the specific FERs responsible for gaps in the FAIRness of a FIP, enabling targeted improvements and informed community decisions. While the FIP Wizard helps communities articulate their FERs, the FIP Check complements it by offering a standardized method to estimate the FAIRness of those choices in practice.

To achieve this, the FIP Check applies questions targeted at each FER type, drawing on established FAIR interpretations and frameworks of Jacobsen et al. (2020) and GO FAIR Foundation (n.d.-d). These targeted questions are detailed in Appendix 1. In particular, the questions are designed to ensure that (1) both FER authors and community-wide independent evaluators can answer them, and (2) a close coupling exists between the FER and its resultant FAIR impact.

3.2. Partial FAIRness

FIP Check recognizes and measures partial FAIRness, offering a structured alternative to the predominantly binary scoring approaches implemented in many current FAIR assessment tools. Existing automated tools, such as F-UJI (Devaraju & Huber, 2020; Devaraju et al., 2020) and FAIR Maturity Indicators (FAIRmetrics & FAIRsharing, n.d.), often evaluate datasets or repositories as compliant or non-compliant with each FAIR principle, even though they acknowledge the concept of FAIRness as a continuum (Candela et al., 2024; FAIRmetrics & FAIRsharing, n.d.).

This all-or-nothing approach supports machine-actionability, enabling clear automated testing and improvement recommendations (Garjio, D., n.d.). However, when the tests fail, the resulting binary outcome may discourage novices to FAIR, rather than guiding them towards progressive, context-appropriate improvements.

FIP Check makes the FAIR continuum visible and inspectable by explicitly applying a progressive scale to FERs. Each FER is assessed using a structured set of FAIR principle-specific questions, with ratings that reflect a progressive level of FAIR alignment (see *Table 1*).

Table 1. Definitions of FAIR Rating Levels.

FAIR Rating	Description
Beginning FAIR	FAIR Principles have not yet been adopted in any significant way. There is little to no use of FAIR-related services. This level represents a starting point with substantial room for improvement.
Basic FAIR	Some initial FAIR-aligned steps have been taken, but adoption is limited and inconsistent. Only a few practices are in place.
Core FAIR	A solid foundation of FAIR implementation exists. Many important elements are implemented, though several areas still need attention. Indicates a clear commitment to FAIR.
Advanced FAIR	FAIR Principles are applied consistently and effectively. Most practices are well established, with only minor gaps remaining.
Exemplary FAIR	Outstanding implementation of FAIR. Practices are comprehensive, effective, and can serve as models for others in the community.

Partial FAIRness makes the current contribution of each FER visible, while also identifying specific, actionable pathways for improvement. By acknowledging partial FAIRness, the FIP Check recognizes resources for their contributions even when not fully aligned with a principle. It also ensures the tone of assessment avoids being judgmental and is constructive; rather than simply flagging deficiencies in a dataset or repository, it provides reasonable insight into how a FER is currently contributing to FAIRness and where enhancements can be made. The tool also provides detailed interpretive scales for certain resources (e.g., Table 2 for F2. Metadata Schema), with explicit anchors for each scale point. This descriptive detail ensures that evaluator estimates of partial alignment are captured precisely.

Table 2. Interpretive Scale for Assessing *F2. Metadata Schema*.

Assessment Aspect	Question	Interpretive Scale
Field Names	Does the metadata schema define structured representations of metadata attributes?	Semantic Standard Standardized Transparent Opaque Absent
Field Values	Does the schema support globally unique, persistent, and resolvable identifiers (GUPRI) for referenced entities?	Formally Profiled Semantic Standard Standardized Described Undefined

Assessment Aspect	Question	Interpretive Scale
Versioning Support	Does the schema support identification and relation of multiple versions of an entity?	Spec + Instance (Internal) Spec (Internal) Spec + Instance (External) Spec (External) None
Community Adoption	Is the schema widely adopted or compatible with community standards?	Standard or International Domain or Nation Multi-Project Project Individual
Findability Attributes	Does the metadata schema include at least 20 attributes to support findability?	20 or more 15 to 19 10 to 14 5 to 9 0 to 4
Schema Representation	Is the schema itself a computable and structured specification that is described with core metadata?	Formally Profiled Semantic Standard Computable Descriptive Absent
Schema Flexibility	Can the metadata schema support optional attributes and multiple-valued attributes?	Optional + Ranged Multiple Optional + Multiple Optional Attribute Repeated Attributes Neither Supported

3.3. Transparent and inspectable balance

FIP Check deliberately balances objective evidence and structured, expert-informed interpretation. While other FAIR assessment approaches (Candela, 2024; FAIRsharing, n.d.) often rely heavily on automated mechanisms, the FIP Check incorporates human input to ensure nuanced and context-aware judgments. It requires individuals who are familiar with the FERs and how those FERs are implemented in the FIP, but it does not require them to be “FAIR experts.” The expertise is embedded in the construction of the FIP Check framework itself—its structured questions and clearly defined scoring anchors—so that assessors with knowledge of any FER can readily provide accurate responses.

With principle-aligned questions and evaluator’s chosen answers visible, FIP Check provides a direct and reviewable link from each score back to the reasoning behind it, and this makes the process transparent and inspectable. FIP Check’s transparency comes from exposing both the criteria and the human judgments applied to them, allowing others to trace, discuss, and refine the results.

By combining verifiable questions with carefully bounded expert input, the FIP Check produces results that are repeatable, verifiable, and responsive to diverse contexts and evolving standards. The framework also creates a pathway toward future automation. Its verifiable questions and rating scales could inform the development of automatic tests in FAIRO or FUJ-I for each FER type, allowing FERs to be annotated with these scores as they are incorporated into a FIP (Fairfication Framework, n.d.).

4. Operational Framework of the FIP Check

Implemented as a Google Sheets-based tool, the core mechanism operates by scoring each FER through target questions, which are organized into dedicated FER-specific tabs (see Figure 2). The results are then automatically pulled into the main “FIP Assessment” tab, where the individual FER scores are combined into an overall FAIRness assessment (see Figure 3). This main tab presents the evaluation structured by FIP, FAIR Principle Category, FAIR Principle, and each FER level, ensuring the full assessment remains transparent and easy to inspect.

F1. Identifier Service						AVERAGE SCORE: 63	Core FAIR	
Service Name	NanoPub ID	1. Does the identifier service provide globally unique identifiers?	2. Are the identifiers persistent over time?	3. Can the identifiers be resolved using standard protocols (e.g., HTTPS) to machine-actionable metadata or digital objects?	4. Does the identifier service guarantee identifier resolution services?	5. Does the identifier service support identification and relation of multiple versions of an entity?	Score	Rating
Identifier-A		Mostly / Strong Support	Yes / Full Support	Partially / Moderate Support	Yes / Full Support	Mostly / Strong Support	80	Advanced FAIR
Identifier-B		Mostly / Strong Support	Partially / Moderate Support	Partially / Moderate Support	Minimally / Weak Support	Partially / Moderate Support	50	Core FAIR
Identifier-C		Mostly / Strong Support	Mostly / Strong Support	Mostly / Strong Support	Partially / Moderate Support	Minimally / Weak Support	60	Core FAIR
Identifier-D		Mostly / Strong Support	Yes / Full Support	Partially / Moderate Support	Mostly / Strong Support	Partially / Moderate Support	70	Advanced FAIR
Identifier-E		Partially / Moderate Support	Partially / Moderate Support	Partially / Moderate Support	Partially / Moderate Support	Mostly / Strong Support	55	Core FAIR

Figure 2. FIP Check Interface - Identifier Service Assessment (F1 Tab), Scoring view for individual identifier services (FERs). Responses to target questions are rated through dropdown options, generating resource-level scores and corresponding FAIR ratings.

FIP Check				Repository FIP		REPO-X			REPO-Y		
FAIR FIP Rating				FIP Rating		Core FAIR			Basic FAIR		
FAIR Level	Min Value	Max Value	FAIR Principle Category	Weight (%)	Average Weighted Score	Unique FERs Count	FAIR Rating	Weighted Score	Unique FERs Count	FAIR Rating	Weighted Score
Exemplary FAIR	85	100	Findability	30	44	4	Core FAIR	56	2	Core FAIR	32
Advanced FAIR	65	85	Accessibility	20	62	4	Core FAIR	62	4	Core FAIR	62
Core FAIR	30	65	Interoperability	30	18	3	Core FAIR	35	0	Beginning FAIR	0
Basic FAIR	10	30	Reusability	20	13	1	Basic FAIR	15	1	Basic FAIR	10
Beginning FAIR	0	10	Overall		33	12		43	7		24

FAIR Principle Category	FAIR Principle	Purpose	Q#	QID	Weight (%)	Average Score	Unique FERs Count	FERs	Score	Unique FERs Count	FERs	Score
Findability	F1. Identifier Service	Metadata	III.1	F1 MD	15	40			0	1	DOI Digital Object Identifier	80
	F1. Identifier Service	Datasets	III.2	F1 D	25	80	1	DOI Digital Object Identifier	80	1	DOI Digital Object Identifier	80
	F2. Metadata Schema		III.3	F2	35	33	1	Provenance, Authority	67			0
	F3. Metadata-Data Linking Schema		III.4	F3	10	0			0			0
Accessibility	F4. Registry	Metadata	III.5	F4 MD	5	42	1	re3data Registry of Identifiers	83			0
	F4. Registry	Datasets	III.6	F4 D	10	42	1	re3data Registry of Identifiers	83			0
	A1.1 Communication Protocol	Metadata	IV.1	A1.1 MD	20	95	1	HTTPS Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure	95	1	HTTPS Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure	95
	A1.1 Communication Protocol	Datasets	IV.2	A1.1 D	35	95	1	HTTPS Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure	95	1	HTTPS Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure	95
Interoperability	A1.2 Authentication & Authorization Service	Metadata	IV.3	A1.2 MD	10	38	1	HTTPS Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure	38	1	HTTPS Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure	38
	A1.2 Authentication & Authorization Service	Datasets	IV.4	A1.2 D	15	38	1	HTTPS Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure	38	1	HTTPS Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure	38
	A2. Metadata Preservation Policy		IV.5	A2	20	0			0			0
	I1. Knowledge Representation Language	Metadata	V.1	I1 MD	10	0			0			0
Reusability	I1. Knowledge Representation Language	Datasets	V.2	I1 D	15	50	2	RDF Resource Description Framework	100			0
	I2. Structured Vocabularies	Metadata	V.3	I2 MD	20	0			0			0
	I2. Structured Vocabularies	Datasets	V.4	I2 D	20	50	1	NCIT National Cancer Institute	100			0
	I3. Semantic Model	Metadata	V.5	I3 MD	15	0			0			0
Reusability	I3. Semantic Model	Datasets	V.6	I3 D	20	0			0			0
	R1.1 Data Usage License	Metadata	VI.1	R1.1 MD	20	0			0			0
	R1.1 Data Usage License	Datasets	VI.2	R1.1 D	20	0			0			0
	R1.2 Metadata Provenance Schema	Metadata	VI.3	R1.2 MD	15	0			0			0
Reusability	R1.2 Metadata Provenance Schema	Datasets	VI.4	R1.2 D	25	0			0			0
	R1.3 Community Use of FIP		VI.5	R1.3	20	63	1	REPO-X	75	1	REPO-Y	50

FER List Question ID	Repo FER Name	Score	FER List Question ID	Repo FER Name	Score
F1 D	DOI Digital Object Identifier	80	F1 MD	DOI Digital Object Identifier	80
F2	Provenance, Authority	67	F1 D	DOI Digital Object Identifier	80
F4 MD	re3data Registry of Identifiers	83	A1.1 MD	HTTPS Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure	95
F4 D	re3data Registry of Identifiers	83	A1.1 D	HTTPS Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure	95
A1.1 MD	HTTPS Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure	95	A1.2 MD	HTTPS Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure	38
A1.1 D	HTTPS Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure	95	A1.2 D	HTTPS Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure	38
A1.2 MD	HTTPS Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure	38	R1.3	REPO-Y	50
A1.2 D	HTTPS Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure	38			
I1 D	RDF Resource Description Framework	100			
I1 D	OWL Web Ontology Language	100			
I2 D	NCIT National Cancer Institute	100			
R1.3	REPO-X	75			

Figure 3. FIP Check Interface - Primary Assessment Tab “FIP Assessment.” This view shows the aggregation of individual FER scores by FAIR Principle and FAIR Principle Category. FIP-level scores (e.g., REPO-X, REPO-Y) are calculated using weighted averages across FAIR domains.

In practice, users start by importing a list of FERs for the FIP they wish to assess. This list can be exported from the FIP Wizard and downloaded as a spreadsheet file. Users then import this file directly into the FIP Assessment tab. Once imported, the main assessment tab displays all the FERs linked to the FIP, showing their current assessment status. If a FER has not yet been assessed by other experts, it will be automatically flagged with a note such as “No FER (score) in [FER tab].” In these cases, the user navigates to the corresponding FER-specific tab, where they complete the principle-aligned questions for that resource. Each FER tab contains a tailored question set relevant to that resource type, with answers scored using one of two assessment schemes (see Table 3), depending on the community’s preference and the level of detail needed. This flexibility allows communities to choose a level of granularity suited to their context, goals, and the level of detail desired.

Table 3. FIP Check Assessment Schemes - Standard (left) and Simplified (right). “Standard Assessment Scheme” uses an ordinal 5-point scale to capture varying degrees of FAIRness. Responses are mapped to scale from 0 (No Support) to 100 (Full Support), with intermediate levels (25, 50, 75) indicating partial alignment. “Simplified Assessment Scheme” applies a binary approach: full or strong support scores 1, while any partial or weak support scores 0.

Support Level	Score Contribution in Standard Assessment	Score Contribution in Simplified Assessment
Yes / Full	100	100
Mostly / Strong	75	100
Partially / Moderate	50	0
Minimally / Weak	25	0
No / No	0	0

Once FERs are scored, FIP Check translates raw scores into a “FAIR Rating” (see Table 4). This translation frames scores in supportive, understandable terms rather than presenting raw numbers alone. By grouping scores into five tiers—Beginning, Basic, Core, Advanced, and Exemplary FAIR—the rating system softens the delivery of results and minimizes score competition or score gaming.

Table 4. FAIR Rating Levels and Score Thresholds

FAIR Ratings	Score Range
Exemplary FAIR	85 - 100
Advanced FAIR	65 - 85
Core FAIR	30 - 65
Basic FAIR	10 - 30
Beginning FAIR	0 - 10

A key feature of the FIP Check is its flexible weighting system, which lets communities adjust how much each FAIR principle or specific criterion contributes to the total score. While we provide suggested (default) weights, these are based on our estimates of the contribution of each FAIR principle to the overall FAIRness of the repository, using both internal analyses and the FAIR Data Maturity Model indicator priority to formulate the final weights. These weights can be customized to match local priorities, project goals, or community requirements, as we did in the first project application. The weights are crucial because they ensure this assessment meaningfully reflects what matters most for a given context.

5. Piloting FIP Check

To explore the practicality of the FIP Check, we conducted a pilot assessment across seven repositories in a biomedical data ecosystem with various levels of FAIR implementation. While these repositories are understood to be in general agreement with the FAIR Principles, the FIP Check allowed us to explore their FAIRness at a more rigorous level. Importantly, this is not a final judgment of FAIR adherence, but a structured investigation of how well specific FERs used by the repositories contribute to FAIRness.

The pilot served as an opportunity to cross-check the levels of FAIRness initially assigned to each FER. While these estimated FAIRness levels are necessarily based on engineering judgment and can continue to be refined over time, low scores sometimes revealed missing or mis-scored FERs, and the resulting overall scores reflected both the maturity of the FIP and its perceived FAIRness. Even in mature FIPs, the FIP Check revealed under-addressed FAIR principles, such as F3, I1, and R1.2, which scored low across all the repositories.

This highlights a key strength of the FIP Check: it surfaces not just which Principles are supported, but how, through specific FERs. Thus, the tool supports both internal reflection and cross-community comparison, fostering targeted improvements to increase interoperability within that community. While we have not explored explicit reporting of cross-community adoption of specific FERs, the resource lists align with previous GO FAIR products that found significant benefits from exposing FER adoption choices to the entire community using the FIP Matrix (GO FAIR, n.d.). We also visualized these numerical assessments using radial charts that summarize each repository's FAIR implementation (see Figure 4).

Figure 4. FIP Check Radial Visualization of REPO-D’s FAIR Alignment. This radar chart visualizes REPO-D’s average scores across individual FAIR principles. Wedge length indicates FAIR alignment, while width reflects each principle’s weight. Each colored wedge represents the four FAIR Principle Categories—Findability (red), Accessibility (yellow), Interoperability (green), and Reusability (blue)—with its length indicating FAIR alignment and its width reflecting its relative weight. The visualization helps clarify differences in emphasis and maturity across principles and repositories. For instance, they can highlight when strong FAIR support in one principle (e.g., A1.1, I2) contrasts with weaker support in another (e.g., F3, R1.2). These insights have prompted discussions among repository stakeholders about prioritizing

specific FAIR improvements, suggesting the tool’s potential to influence implementation decisions over time.

6. Discussion

6.1. Emerging Strengths of the FIP Check

FIP Check demonstrated several strengths in its broader application beyond individual repository or digital object assessment. By assessing FERs as declared in a FIP, it enabled evaluation of the FIP as a whole, but also supported comparative analyses that revealed meaningful trends across the ecosystem. By averaging scores across FIPs, we could identify which FAIR principles were commonly supported and which lacked concrete FERs. These comparisons—some visualized in appendices 2 to 4—also allowed us to compare scores against peer repositories similarly as done for the ENVRI-FAIR communities (Peterseil *et al.*, 2023).

This comparative lens is a powerful feature of the FIP Check. It moves beyond static scoring to support analysis of systemic trends, implementation strategies, and community norms across the FIP ecosystem. It highlights improvements in the selection or quality of FERs—such as adopting more FAIR-aligned resources or enhancing interoperability of FERs. Community members will have a concrete reference point to guide discussions—internally, with other community members, or with external stakeholders.

This can foster greater community communication, adoption of common and increasingly FAIR implementations, and prioritization of efforts that create appropriate FAIRness.

These comparisons may also inform the structure of the FAIR Principles themselves, offering insight into how FAIRness is implemented and understood in practice. For example, the FAIR principle R1.2 Metadata Provenance Schema often captures resources describing data but not metadata. This matches our intuition that metadata-related Principles would be supported in fewer repositories (the ones with more advanced metadata management) than the corresponding principles about data.

6.2. Interpretive Decisions and Methodological Considerations

Several interpretive decisions were necessary in designing and applying the FIP Check. One important decision involved how FAIR Principles are prioritized; assessing the R1.3 Community Use of FIP principle proved challenging. The FAIR principle states “(Meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards” (GO FAIR Foundation, n.d.-c), and the FIP Wizard assumes that anyone filling out a FIP is declaring those standards, so it asks no questions.

However, FIP Check treats this question as an opportunity to characterize the repository’s level of adoption of its declared FERs. The FIP Check evaluation of this FER, which is always the repository itself, contains a single question—“Are the FAIR Enabling Resources described in this profile used/followed throughout the described project or system?”—and the answer affects only the R1.3 score. This scoring approach may still understate the broader influence of R1.3 across the FIP, and future work—such as ongoing developments in FAIR2Adapt (European Commission, 2024)—aims to address this more comprehensively.

6.3. Structural and technical limitations

FIP Check assessments do not represent the complete spectrum of FAIRness concerns, and should not be interpreted as a complete or authoritative result. In addition, while some community initiatives (Gargio, n.d.) are developing shared frameworks, there is currently no “gold standard” for FAIR assessment against which to benchmark the FIP-based approach. While the FIP Check team has conducted extensive internal reviews, no formal statistical evaluations have been performed, and engineering judgments—such as FAIR Principle and Category weights and FER FAIRness assessments—have not been externally reviewed.

FIP declarations allow users to indicate when an FER is proposed but not yet in use. This is important for supporting transparent community communication around FER choices. However, the current version of FIP Check assumes that all FERs listed in the FIP are implemented. This limitation can affect assessment accuracy; therefore, the FIP Check should represent such distinctions by indicating the FIP Check result both with and without the planned FERs.

Technical scalability is another constraint. The current Google Sheets format cannot sustainably support large numbers of repositories. A shift to a database-backed application with semi-automation would be required for broader adoption, and an inclusion as annotations in the FIP Wizard would be valuable. On the other hand, its value is demonstrated within the context of the original project, where we performed a detailed comparison and analysis of seven repositories without issue.

Finally, ensuring consistency across the tool becomes increasingly important. While the rubric provides a structured foundation, interpretations can vary. Incorporating inter-expert agreement, shared scoring guidance, or even peer-review mechanisms—potentially in combination with the GO FAIR Foundation’s

FSR Curation Pipeline (GO FAIR Foundation, n.d.-b)—could help improve consistency and trustworthiness in the assessments. Future directions include exploring foundational model approaches for scalable alignment.

7. Conclusion

We introduce FIP Check, a novel tool for assessing FAIRness of FIPs and FERs. FIP Check embeds certain conceptual innovations, allowing for precise interventions, accounting for partial FAIRness, and being flexible enough for different communities of experts. We have explained how the FIP Check works in practice and how it was tested through the pilot assessment of seven repositories. Its outputs can be visualized to inform diverse stakeholders—from data scientists to managers and funders—and its metrics can be tailored to reflect the priorities of its users. This paper marks only the beginning of the FIP Check’s development; maintained openly within GO FAIR US GitHub (GO FAIR US, 2025) and in collaboration with allied projects, its design and impact will continue to evolve as more researchers, organizations, and communities engage with and refine the approach. Interested communities and tool developers are encouraged to review, integrate, and contact the authors.

References

- Candela, L., Mangione, D., & Pavone, G. (2024). The FAIR Assessment Conundrum: Reflections on Tools and Metrics. *Data Science Journal*, 23(33). DOI: [10.5334/dsj-2024-033](https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2024-033).
- Devaraju, A., & Huber, R. (2020). F-UJI - An Automated FAIR Data Assessment Tool. Zenodo. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.6361400](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6361400).
- Devaraju, A., Huber, R., Mokrane, M., Herterich, P., Cepinskas, L., de Vries, J., L'Hours, H., Davidson, J., & Angus White. (2020). FAIRsFAIR Data Object Assessment Metrics (0.4). Zenodo. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4081213](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4081213).
- European Commission. (2024, October). FAIR to Adapt to Climate Change (FAIR2Adapt), European Commission. DOI: [10.3030/101188256](https://doi.org/10.3030/101188256).
- FAIRification Framework. (n.d.). Fairification Framework Architecture. Retrieved August 11, 2025, from <https://fairification-framework.readthedocs.io/en/latest/architecture/>.
- FAIRmetrics & FAIRsharing. (n.d.). FAIR Evaluation Services. FAIRsharing. Retrieved June 26, 2025, from <https://fairsharing.github.io/FAIR-Evaluator-FrontEnd>.
- FAIRsharing. (n.d.). Tools. FAIRassist. Retrieved August 11, 2025, from <https://fairassist.org/tools>.
- Gaignard, A., Rosnet, T., de Lamotte, F., Lefort, V., & Devignes, M. (2023). FAIR-Checker: supporting digital resource findability and reuse with Knowledge Graphs and Semantic Web standards. *Journal of Biomedical Semantics*, 14. DOI: [10.1186/s13326-023-00289-5](https://doi.org/10.1186/s13326-023-00289-5).
- Gargio, D. (n.d.). Architecture: FAIR-IF. OS Trails. Retrieved August 11, 2025, from https://docs.ostrails.eu/en/update-restructure/architecture/fair_if.html#fair-reference-model-conceptual-components.
- GO FAIR. (n.d.). FAIR Convergence Matrix & FAIR Implementation Profiles. Retrieved August 11, 2025, from <https://www.go-fair.org/today/fair-matrix/>.
- GO FAIR Foundation (n.d.-a). FIP Wizard (Version 4.0). <https://fip.fair-wizard.com/>.
- GO FAIR Foundation. (n.d.-b). FSR Curation. GitHub. https://github.com/gofair-foundation/fsr_curation.
- GO FAIR Foundation. (n.d.-c). Interpreting FAIR. Retrieved August 11, 2025, from <https://www.gofair.foundation/interpretation>.
- GO FAIR US. (2025). FIP-Check. GitHub. <https://github.com/go-fair-us/fip-check>.
- Hoebelheinrich, N.J., Graybeal, J., Kherroubi, I.G., Christopher, J., Christopher, E., & Kirkpatrick, C. (2025). A persona-specific method to assess the FAIRness of data repositories. [Preprint]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13992885>.
- Jacobsen, A., de Miranda Azevedo, R., Juty, N., Batista, D., Coles, S., Cornet, R., Courtot, M., Crosas, M., Dumontier, M., Evelo, C. T., Goble, C., Guizzardi, G., Kryger Hansen, K., Hasnain, A., Hettne, K., Heringa, J., Hooft, R. W. W., Imming, M., Jeffery, K. G., Kaliyaperumal, R., Kersloot, M. G., Kirkpatrick, C. R., Kuhn, T., Labastida, I., Magagna, B., McQuilton, P., Meyers, N., Montesanti, A., van Reisen, M., Rocca-Serra, P., Pergl, R., Sansone, S.-A., da Silva Santos, L. O. B., Schneider, J., Strawn, G., Thompson, M., Waagmeester, A., Weigel, T., Wilkinson, M. D., Willighagen, E. L., Wittenburg, P., Roos, M., Mons, B., & Schultes, E. (2020). FAIR Principles: Interpretations and Implementation Considerations. *Data Intelligence*, 2(1-2). 10-29. https://doi.org/10.1162/dint_r_00024.

- Kang, S., (2025). FIP Check. Nanodash. <https://w3id.org/np/RA-vzI2L0BwYK-m6VAbAXBtuTNK6heUsFHwqgRvrvHmuw>.
- Maastricht University. (n.d.). FAIR enough. Retrieved August 12, 2025, from <https://fair-enough.semanticscience.org/>.
- Magagna, B., Schultes, E., & Kuhn, T. (n.d.). FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP) Ontology. Retrieved August 11, 2025, from <https://peta-pico.github.io/FAIR-nanopubs/fip/index-en.html>.
- Magagna, B., Schultes, E., Fouilloux, A., Burger, G., Devriendt, D., Bramley, R., Kuhn, T., Moreira, J.L.R., da Silva Santos, L.O.B., & Pires, L.F., (2024). Ontological Analysis of FAIR Supporting Resources, FOAM: FAIR Principles for Ontologies and Metadata in Knowledge Management Workshop, JOWO 2024, Enschede. <https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-3882/foam-5.pdf>.
- Peterseil, J., Offenthaler, I., Wohner, C., Magagna, B., Schultes, E., Lund Myhre, C., Jeffery, K., Bailo, D., Dobler, D., Portier, M., Dema, C., Vaira, L., & Rosati, I. (2023). ENVRI-FAIR D5.6: Synthesis and future strategy (1.1). Zenodo. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.10363036](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10363036).
- Wilkinson, M. D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. J. J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., Baak, A., Blomberg, N., Boiten, J.-W., da Silva Santos, L. B., Bourne, P. E., Bouwman, J., Brookes, A. J., Clark, T., Crosas, M., Dillo, I., Dumon, O., Edmunds, S., Evelo, C. T., Finkers, R., Gonzalez-Beltran, A., Gray, A. J. G., Groth, P., Goble, C., Grethe, J. S., Heringa, J., 't Hoen, P. A. C., Hooft, R., Kuhn, T., Kok, R., Kok, J., Lusher, S. J., Martone, M. E., Mons, A., Packer, A. L., Persson, B., Rocca-Serra, P., Roos, M., van Schaik, R., Sansone, S.-A., Schultes, E., Sengstag, T., Slater, T., Strawn, G., Swertz, M. A., Thompson, M., van der Lei, J., van Mulligen, E., Velterop, J., Waagmeester, A., Wittenburg, P., Wolstencroft, K., Zhao, J., & Mons, B. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data*, 3, 160018. DOI: [10.1038/sdata.2016.18](https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18).

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Appendix

Appendix 1. FAIR Enabling Resources: Definitions and Assessment Questions

FAIR principle	FAIR Enabling Resource Type	Description	Assessment Questions
F1	Identifier Service	A service that provides for any digital object (1) algorithms guaranteeing global uniqueness, (2) a policy document that guarantees persistence, and (3) resolution of the identifier to machine-actionable metadata describing the object and its location.	<p>Does the identifier service provide globally unique identifiers?</p> <p>Are the identifiers persistent over time?</p> <p>Can the identifiers be resolved using standard protocols (e.g., HTTPs) to machine-actionable metadata or digital objects?</p> <p>Does the identifier service guarantee identifier resolution services?</p> <p>Does the identifier service support identification and relation of multiple versions of an entity?</p>
F2	Metadata Schema	A specification that specifies the structured representation of metadata describing attributes of data or other digital objects in terms of semantics, syntax, and optionality.	<p>Does the metadata schema define structured representations of metadata attributes?</p> <p>Does the schema support globally unique, persistent, and resolvable identifiers (GUPRI) for referenced entities?</p> <p>Does the schema support identification and relation of multiple versions of an entity?</p> <p>Is the schema widely adopted or compatible with community standards?</p> <p>Does the metadata schema include at least 20 attributes to support findability?</p> <p>Is the schema itself a computable and structured specification that is described with core metadata?</p> <p>Can the metadata schema support optional attributes and multiple attributes?</p>

FAIR principle	FAIR Enabling Resource Type	Description	Assessment Questions
F3	Metadata-Data Linking Schema	A specification that provides a unique, persistent, (ideally) bi-directional, machine-actionable link between metadata and the data they describe.	<p>Does the linking approach enforce GUPRI identifiers that link the data to the associated metadata?</p> <p>Does the linking approach enforce GUPRI identifiers that link the metadata to the associated data?</p> <p>Is the linking approach compliant with widely accepted practices for linking metadata and data?</p> <p>Can the linking approach handle multiple versions or updates of both metadata and data?</p>
F4	Registry	A service that indexes metadata and data and provides a search over index.	<p>Does the registry provide a FAIR community metadata standard to be used when uploading data?</p> <p>Does the registry provide unique identifiers for data uploaded and metadata created?</p> <p>Does the registry provide indexing services for the metadata and data it registers?</p> <p>Does the registry include mechanisms for categorizing, tagging, and ranking resources, using defined concepts with identifiers?</p> <p>Is the registry searchable via user interface and machine-actionable protocols?</p> <p>Does the registry expose metadata records in standard formats?</p>

FAIR principle	FAIR Enabling Resource Type	Description	Assessment Questions
A1.1	Communication Protocol	A specification of how messages are structured and exchanged.	<p>Is the retrieval communication protocol standardized and openly described, and implemented?</p> <p>Does the protocol support both human and machine interactions?</p> <p>Does the protocol support both data and metadata retrieval?</p> <p>Does the protocol allow GUPRI identifiers for accessed resources?</p> <p>Is the protocol broadly adopted across domains and communities?</p>
A1.2	Authentication & Authorization Service	A service that mediates access to digital objects according to specified conditions	<p>Does the service mediate controlled access to digital objects?</p> <p>Is appropriate metadata accessible even when authentication is required for data access?</p>
A2	Metadata Preservation Policy	A data policy that describes the conditions under which metadata should be provided in the future.	<p>Does the policy address long-term preservation of metadata?</p> <p>Does the policy call for metadata preservation practices to follow recognized best practices?</p> <p>Does the policy establish requirements for backups?</p> <p>Does the policy require metadata remain accessible even if the data object becomes unavailable?</p> <p>Is the policy formally endorsed or maintained by a community organization or standards body?</p>

FAIR principle	FAIR Enabling Resource Type	Description	Assessment Questions
I1	Knowledge Representation Language	A language specification that enables knowledge to be processed by machines.	<p>Does the KR language enable knowledge to be processed by machines (e.g., RDF, OWL)?</p> <p>Is the KR language representation compatible with established semantic web standards?</p> <p>Can the KR language be extended to new use cases without losing interoperability?</p>
I2	Structured Vocabularies	A specification for a controlled list of uniquely identified and unambiguous concepts with their definitions represented using web standards.	<p>Is the vocabulary representation compliant with established semantic web standards (e.g., SKOS, OWL, RDF)?</p> <p>Does the vocabulary provide labels and definitions for all its concepts?</p> <p>Is the vocabulary openly maintained and accessible with rich metadata in a public repository?</p> <p>Does the vocabulary's public repository support persistent and resolvable identifiers, versioning information, and provenance tracking?</p> <p>Is the vocabulary endorsed or maintained by a community organization or standards body?</p>

FAIR principle	FAIR Enabling Resource Type	Description	Assessment Questions
I3	Semantic Model	A specification that defines qualified relations between entities describing data or other digital objects according to the Linked Data principles. This can include semantic data models and ontologies.	<p>Is the model representation compliant with established semantic web standards?</p> <p>Is the model openly maintained and accessible with rich metadata in a public repository?</p> <p>Does the semantic model's public repository support persistent and resolvable identifiers, versioning information, and provenance tracking?</p> <p>Does the model provide labels and definitions for all its concepts?</p> <p>Does the model integrate data from multiple sources seamlessly and define qualified relations between entities?</p> <p>Is the semantic model endorsed or maintained by a community organization or standards body?</p>
R1.1	Data Usage License	A data policy that specifies legal restrictions on the reuse of the data.	<p>Does the license have an associated GUPRI identifier(s)? (Example: SPDX identifiers like those from https://spdx.org/licenses/)</p> <p>Is the license available in a machine-readable format?</p> <p>Does the license clearly support any reuse of the data or metadata artifacts it describes?</p> <p>Does the license clearly support (at least) limited or qualified reuse of the data or metadata artifacts it describes?</p>

FAIR principle	FAIR Enabling Resource Type	Description	Assessment Questions
R1.2	Provenance Model	A specification that specifies metadata describing the origin and lineage of data or other digital objects.	<p>Does the provenance model describe the origin and lineage of the data, metadata, and other digital objects?</p> <p>Does the provenance model include linkage to the described resource(s)?</p> <p>Is the provenance model compatible with recognized community standards?</p> <p>Is the provenance model a specified, computable model described with core metadata and its own GUPRI identifier?</p>
R1.3	Community Use of FIP	A FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP) is a list of declared technology choices intended to implement each of the FAIR Guiding Principles, made as a collective decision by the members of a particular community of practice.	<p>Are the FAIR Enabling Resources described in this profile used/followed throughout the described project or system?</p>

Appendix 2. Visualization of FIP-Level Assessment Comparison: REPO-C and REPO-D

Appendix 3. Visualization of Division-Level Assessment: DIV-ALPHA and DIV-BETA

Appendix 4. Visualization of Repository and Division Average: REPO-D and DIV-BETA

This figure compares REPO-D’s FIP Check FIP Assessment to the average scores of its parent division, DIV-BETA. Colored wedges represent REPO-D’s scores across the four FAIR dimensions, while the semi-transparent gray wedges show the average scores of all repositories within DIV-BETA.

